

EARTH SCIENCES

TRANSFORMATION OF GRAVIMAGNETIC ANOMALIES ON THE COMPUTER

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Abstract

The observed gravity field is usually complex because it consists of local and regional gravity components that correspond to local and regional geological structures. Local geological objects are objects of small size and located at shallow depths in sedimentary strata. Regional anomalies reflect the deep structure of the earth's crust. Transformation is the process of transforming an observed complex field in order to separate it into its constituent elements. At the Department of Geophysics of ASOIU, the Force-Fortran program OSRED has been developed, which allows you to perform transformation using the method of averaging over an area. The article provides a description of this program and the results of its application on model materials.

Keywords: anomaly, field transformation, palette, transformation radius, calculation algorithm, local anomaly, observed field.

Introduction.

Gravimagnetic prospecting, being one of the methods of geophysics, currently successfully solves geological problems related to the structure of the earth's crust and its sedimentary strata based on studying the nature of local and regional anomalies of gravitational and magnetic fields, which are identified by transforming complex observed fields [1]. There are various methods for transforming gravimagnetic fields [9,11]: a graphical method, which is used in the case of a simple linear field, that is, when the regional field changes linearly along the profile; method of averaging

over area or profile; gradient method (Sakov-Nygaard); method of higher derivatives; methods of analytical continuation of fields into upper and lower half-spaces, etc. The initial data is the gravity Bouguer anomaly or the magnetic field anomaly.

In the area averaging method, in order to perform a transformation at each point in the field, a palette made on tracing paper is used (Fig. 1). The radius of the circles depends on the task at hand. The larger the radius, the greater the depth of exploration. The observed field anomaly is the sum of the regional and local anomaly:

Fig.1. Transformation palette

$$\Delta g_{ob} = \Delta g_{reg} + \Delta g_{loc} \quad (1)$$

From this:

$$\Delta g_{loc} = \Delta g_{ob} - \Delta g_{reg} \quad (2)$$

The regional component of the field is calculated using the following form

$$\Delta g_{reg} = \Delta g_{av} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \Delta g_i}{n}, \quad (3)$$

Here n is the number of points on the palette; Δg_{av} is average field value in the center of the palette; Δg_i is the value of gravity at points around the palette. Currently, this transformation method is carried out on a computer. In this case, to enter field values into a computer, the original field is first quantized by interpolation at the nodes of a square grid (Fig. 2). As a result of the transformation, two maps are obtained: map Δg_{per} and $\Delta g_{лок}$.

Fig.2. Field quantization nodes

Algorithm for transformation of gravimagnetic fields averaging method

When transforming gravimagnetic fields on a computer, either by averaging or by other transformation methods, the maps of the observed fields are quantized with a uniform step (usually equal to 1 cm of the map scale). When transforming gravimagnetic fields using the averaging method, the values of the observed field g_{ij} are averaged at the nodal points of the circular palette and the difference is formed

between the observed value in the center of the palette g_{oi} and the averaged value $\overline{g_{oi}}$. The choice of radii of the averaging palette is made both according to

the spectral composition of gravimagnetic anomalies and taking into account the depth of occurrence of the studied sediment complexes. The Department of Geophysics of ASOIU has developed the OSRED algorithm and the corresponding Forse-Fortran program, the block diagram of which is shown in Figure. 3. This program allows you to transform gravimagnetic fields using the averaging method using two radii of a circular palette - the inner radius $R_1 = 2\sqrt{2}$ km and the outer radius $R_2 = 5$ km [2-8,10]. Using the OSRED program, the values of the observed gravitational or magnetic fields and the dimensions of the averaging area are first entered. These values are then printed

Fig.3. OSRED program block-diagram

to verify the correctness of the data. Next, the average value of the field at each radius is calculated over four points, and then the average value is calculated over two radii. The resulting value is taken as the average value of the regional field. To calculate the local component of the potential field, the difference between the observed field value at the center of the palette and the calculated average value is found. In order to obtain separate maps of local anomalies and the regional background, the program calculates the regional field once and the local anomalies another time. The resulting field values are printed digitally. Next, based on the obtained values, maps of local and regional fields are constructed using a graphical program.

Results of transformation of the gravitational field model

computer averaging method

To work with the OSRED program, a model of the gravitational field was first compiled in milligal isolines, which was quantized at the nodes of a square grid with a step of 1 cm by linear interpolation. Figure 4 shows the gravity values at the quantization points. For a visual representation, the original map was digitized in the "Digit" mode of the SURFER graphic program, and then a grid was created, on the basis of which maps of the original gravitational field model

were built in 2D and 3D versions in a modern interface (Fig. 5-6). As you can see, the map cross-section is 0.5 mGal, and the gravity values decrease from northwest to southeast in the range from 4 mGal to -4 mGal. The isolines are oriented mainly in the southwest - northeast direction, forming complications in the form of protrusions in the central part of the gravity field model. The quantized values of this field were entered into the OSRED program, with the help of which the values of the regional gravity field were calculated and the corresponding maps of the regional field were constructed (Fig. 7-9). As can be seen, the regional gravity anomaly smoothly decreases from northwest to southeast in the same interval as the original field, reflecting the regional structure of the proposed geological model. Figures 10-12 show the calculated values of the local gravity anomaly and the constructed maps of the local gravity anomaly in areal and spatial form. As can be seen, in the western and northwestern parts of the original field there is a clear negative gravity anomaly (minimum gravity) with an intensity of approximately 0.7 mGal and an amplitude of approximately 0.5 mGal, oriented in the meridional direction. In the right part of the original field, a relative gravity maximum of irregular shape with an intensity of 0.3 mGal and an amplitude of approximately 0.1 mGal and oriented partially in the northeast direction.

3.9	3.6	3.3	3.0	2.7	2.4	2.1	1.9	1.6	1.3	1.1	0.7
3.6	3.1	2.9	2.6	2.3	2.0	1.8	1.5	1.2	1.0	0.6	0.4
3.2	2.9	2.5	2.1	1.9	1.6	1.4	1.1	0.9	0.9	0.2	0.0
2.8	2.5	2.2	1.5	1.0	0.9	0.9	0.7	0.4	0.1	-0.1	-1.0
2.5	2.2	1.9	1.0	0.5	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.0	-0.5	-1.0	-1.1
2.2	2.0	1.4	0.8	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.3	-0.6	-1.0	-1.2	-1.6
1.9	1.5	1.0	0.2	-0.2	-0.4	-0.6	-0.9	-1.0	-1.3	-1.6	-1.9
1.5	1.3	0.9	0.2	-0.2	-0.6	-0.9	-1.1	-1.5	-1.7	-1.9	-2.2
1.2	1.0	0.6	0.1	-0.4	-0.9	-1.1	-1.6	-2.0	-2.3	-2.8	-3.0
0.9	0.7	0.3	0.0	-0.6	-1.1	-1.5	-1.9	-2.4	-3.0	-3.2	-3.5
0.5	0.2	0.0	-0.5	-0.9	-1.2	-1.6	-1.9	-2.5	-3.1	-3.5	-3.8
0.0	-0.1	-0.4	-0.9	-1.1	-1.5	-1.9	-2.1	-2.8	-3.2	-3.7	-4.0

Fig. 4. Model of the gravitational field in digital form

Fig.5. Map of a digital field model in 2D version (isolines in mGal units)

Fig. 6. Map of the digital field model in 3D version (isolines in mGal units)

2.4	2.1	1.9	1.5	1.2	0.9	0.6	0.4
2.0	1.8	1.5	1.1	0.7	0.5	0.3	0.0
1.7	1.4	1.1	0.6	0.4	0.2	-0.2	-0.4
1.3	1.0	0.8	0.3	-0.1	-0.3	-0.5	-0.9
0.9	0.6	0.4	-0.1	-0.5	-0.9	-1.2	-1.4
0.6	0.4	0.0	-0.3	-0.9	-1.3	-1.5	-1.8
0.3	0.0	-0.3	-0.8	-1.1	-1.5	-1.8	-2.1
0.1	-0.2	-0.6	-1.0	-1.4	-1.8	-2.1	-2.3

Fig.7. Regional gravity anomaly values from the results calculations using the OSRED program in digital form.

Fig.8. Map of the digital model of the regional field in 2D version (isolines in mGal units)

Fig.9. Map of the digital model of the regional field in 3D version (isolines in mGal units)

0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.5
0.2	-0.3	-0.5	-0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1
0.2	-0.4	-0.6	-0.3	-0.2	0.0	0.2	-0.1
0.1	-0.2	-0.8	-0.4	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-0.1
0.1	-0.4	-0.6	-0.3	-0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1
0.3	-0.2	-0.2	-0.3	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.1
0.3	0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	-0.2	-0.2
0.3	0.2	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.2	-0.3	-0.7

Fig. 10. Values of local gravity anomaly according to the results calculations using the OSRED program in digital form (isolines in mGal units)

Fig. 11. Map of the digital model of the local field in 2D version (isolines in mGal units)

Fig. 12. Map of the digital model of the local field in 3D version (isolines in mGal units)

Conclusions

1. Transformation of gravimagnetic fields is a very important stage in the processing and interpretation of the initial observed potential field, which makes it possible to separate a complex field into regional and local components. These field components reflect the geological structure of the earth's crust, including sedimentary strata.

2. The algorithm and block diagram of the Forsee-Fortran program OSRED, developed at the Department of Geophysics of ASOIU, is described, which allows the transformation of gravimagnetic fields by the averaging method using two radii of a circular palette.

3. A digital model of the gravitational field was constructed, which was quantized in square grid nodes with a step of 1 cm by linear interpolation for working with the OSRED program.

4. The values of regional and local gravity anomalies were calculated using the OSRED program and

the corresponding grids of these anomalies were prepared for constructing the corresponding maps using the Surfer graphics program.

5. Maps of regional and local gravity anomalies in areal and spatial form were constructed and analyzed. The local anomaly map shows a gravity minimum with an intensity of approximately 0.7 mGal and an amplitude of approximately 0.5 mGal, oriented in the meridional direction, and a relative gravity maximum of an irregular shape with an intensity of 0.3 mGal and an amplitude of approximately 0.1 mGal, oriented partly in a north-east direction.

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